

First record of *Thaumastocoris peregrinus* Carpintero & Dellapé, 2006 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Thaumastocoridae) in Algeria

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ABSTRACT: The first record of the alien *Thaumastocoris peregrinus* Carpintero & Dellapé, 2006 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Thaumastocoridae) in Algeria is reported. The distribution of the species in the Mediterranean Region is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Thaumastocoris peregrinus*, invasive species, first record, distribution, Algeria, Mediterranean Region.

The Australian bronze bug *Thaumastocoris peregrinus* Carpintero & Dellapé, 2006 (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Thaumastocoridae) was described based on specimens found in Argentina (Carpintero & Dellapé, 2006). The species is a serious pest on *Eucalyptus* species (Myrtaceae) (van der Heyden, 2021). Sardinia (di Lascio & Nannini, 2016), Portugal (Garcia et al., 2013), Spain (Vivas et al., 2015), Israel (Novoselsky & Freidberg, 2016), Albania (van der Heyden, 2017), mainland Greece and several Greek islands (Petrakis, 2018), including Crete (van der Heyden, 2021), Malta (Mifsud & Carapezza, 2020), Cyprus (Demetriou et al., 2023) and Syria (Zeity et al., 2023), so far. Furthermore, *T. peregrinus* was reported from the island of Gran Canaria (Canary Islands, Spain) (van der Heyden, 2023).

In the Mediterranean Region, *T. peregrinus* has been reported from mainland Italy (Laudonia & Sasso, 2012) and the Italian islands of Sicily (Carapezza, 2014) and

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Herein, the first record of *T. peregrinus* in Algeria is reported: On 28.11.2024, an adult specimen (Fig. 1) was observed and photographed in the city of Constantine, located about 80 km from the Mediterranean Sea. Four related photos were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Filali, 2024).

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Thaumastocoris peregrinus* Carpintero & Dellapé, 2006, Constantine, Algeria, 28.11.2024. (Photo: Aissa Filali).

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